

Research on Artificial Intelligence Applications in the Hotel Industry: A Bibliometric Study

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to provide a bibliometric analysis of the literature on artificial intelligence applications in the hotel sector. The evaluation is conducted on 750 papers published between 1984 and 2025. The study looks for the most prominent journals in this field, the most published years, the most referenced articles, key authors, and the most productive nations and organizations. Network maps of co-authorship and keyword co-occurrences are also reported.

Approach, Methodology, and Design: The extensive data from the several papers that were part of this study was analyzed using the Scopus database. Co-authorship network maps, inter-country co-authorship network maps, and keyword co-occurrences network maps were all made using the VOSviewer software.

Findings: The findings show that the greatest number of publications were published in 2024. *International The Journal*

of Contemporary Hospitality Management and *Computer Science Lecture Notes with Subseries* The two most important journals are *Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics* and *Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence*. The most cited paper is the “Effect of Covid-19 on hotel marketing and management: A perspective article.” Additionally, the most well-known writer is Ivanov, S., and the nation with the highest rate of production and institutions are China and The Hong Kong Polytechnic university, in turn.

Originality/value: This research adds to the body of knowledge on artificial intelligence and hotels. Using bibliometric tools, a thorough and trustworthy image of this field is provided. The findings may act as a guide for authors who wish to conduct additional study on this topic in the future.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Hotels, Hotel Industry, VOS viewer, Bibliometric Analysis

1. Introduction:

In academic research, literature reviews are crucial for assessing the overall state of a field, compiling and classifying existing knowledge, and identifying knowledge gaps that need to be filled (Öztürk et al., 2024). Scientific knowledge is growing exponentially as a result of the recent sharp increase in the quantity of scholarly publications, conferences, and further publications channels. Papers (such as articles, reports, and conference papers) are published in numbers exceeding millions annually (Kraus et al., 2022). Therefore, choosing the papers that will be used to analyse the literature on the pertinent topic is essential for a researcher. Many reviews leave it up to the reader to evaluate the writers' reasons for including (or excluding) particular books, conference papers, or articles (Linnenluecke et al., 2020). Researchers frequently reference evidence from "high-quality" publications without necessarily taking a broader range of information into account. As a result, it is presently highly challenging for researchers to classify the corpus of information in a particular field with the use of conventional review of the literature techniques (such as critical, meta-, and narrative-analysis), identify gaps, and track the state, advances, and progress of the field. As a result, Bibliometric evaluation, which permits a review to take into account all of the literature that is pertinent to any field of study, has drawn increased interest.

A key tool to evaluate the academic outputs of various scientific items (such as papers, authors, keywords, journals, institutions, and nations) in any field of study is bibliometric analysis, which also looks at how the intellectual, social, and conceptual structure of the field has changed over time based on the connections and interactions between these items (Donthu et al., 2021). In the previous several decades, the service sector's position in modern society has expanded.

Customer-oriented sectors that are specifically tied to meeting their demands and innovations targeted at the hotel industry seem to be very promising and well-liked by consumers among the different sectors where artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have been used successfully (Citak et al., 2021). By using AI to optimise on-site services and operations, hotels may improve customer (guest) encounters. In order to preserve overall quality, staying in touch with visitors and attending to their requirements. When the concept of a smart hotel was first proposed, scholars took a keen interest in it (Buhalis et al., 2019). Various intelligent technologies and tools, machine learning, artificial neural networks, big data, the Internet of Things, smart robotics, and applications for virtual and augmented reality are all included in artificial intelligence (AI) (Li et al., 2019). Expanding processing capacity, the accessibility of massive sets of data, and improvements in machine-learning models and algorithms are all contributing to the increasing importance of AI. It is dependent upon massive algorithms, data, and processing power to carry out a number of difficult tasks (including collecting, analyzing, and processing data) that would require clever work if done by people. These duties impact relationships between service providers and customers, form the basis of several intelligence services and operations, and have wide-ranging effects on marketing, operations, service, and management (Knani et al., 2022).

Especially in the past four years, as professionals and scholars have grown increasingly interested in AI, research on its application in the hotel sector has increased. It is essential to review the topic of development, evaluate the pertinent prior research, and propose new research directions in order to comprehend the fundamental ideas and the flow of knowledge around artificial intelligence.

Thus, the following objectives lead this bibliometric analysis: (i) to measure the amount of Articles on artificial intelligence published in the travel and hospitality industry; (ii) to determine and analyse the most essential subjects and to create a thematic map of AI research; (iii) to suggest Future directions for AI development and research in hotels; and (iii) to explain the major scholarly publications, writers, nations, and organizations that publish in this area, together with the most important papers and author networks. This research adds to the body of literature on hotel industry by finding indicators, subjects, and patterns that represent the current level of understanding in AI research and by promoting additional study.

The following questions are intended to be addressed in this paper:

Q1. Which journals have released the most papers about hotels and artificial intelligence?

Q2. In which years have the most papers been published?

Q3. Which papers receive the most citations?

Q4. Which writers are the most common?

Q5. Which countries and institutions are the most common?

Q6. Which writers have collaborated alongside other writers the most?

Q7: Which nations' writers have collaborated with other nations' writers the most?

Q8. What are the keywords that appear most often?

The remaining section of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the study's research methodology and process, and Section 3 presents the results and findings of this analysis, in light of the study's goals and research questions. The discussion, conclusions, and limitations of this study are finally presented in Section 4.

- Most prolific writers;

2. Research Methodology

The research on artificial intelligence applications in the hotel industry from 1984 to 2025 is examined in this paper using bibliometric analysis. The Scopus database was searched up until March 14, 2025. The pattern of publications on a particular topic, the tendency for publishing within a subject, and the quantitative changes in a research discipline are all commonly ascertained by bibliometric analysis (De Bakker et al., 2005). For experts and professionals intrigued by evaluating such research activity, the findings of such analysis provide timely, practical, and helpful information (Edison Jair Duque Oliva, Amparo Cervera Taulet, 2006). As another advantage, bibliometric analysis also allows a specific discipline's objective examination in a quantitative manner (Merigó et al., 2015).

The database Scopus was utilized to find the papers that discussed artificial intelligence's use in lodging facilities and were published between 1984 and 2025. This database was selected because of its

expanded coverage of prestigious journals. We looked for papers with the conditions "artificial intelligence" and "hotels." The search filter only turned up papers that contained the terms "artificial intelligence" and "hotels" in their keywords, abstract, or title.

Additionally, the search turned up 750 documents in total. To make sure The papers found through the search were pertinent to the intended topic, the author carefully examined every paper's title, abstract, and keywords.

Additionally, these papers are categorized using:

- Journals with the most number of publications;
- Publishing by year;
- Most papers that are cited;

- Most thriving nations and establishment;
- Examination of international co-authorship networks; and
- Inter country co-authorship network analysis; and
- Co-occurrence analysis of keywords in a network.

The VOS Viewer 1.6.20 software was utilized for analyzing co-authorship networks, analyzing co-authorship networks across nations, and keywords co-occurrences analysis of networks.

3. Results and Findings:

3.1 Journals with the most publications

All the 750 papers in this study belong to their respective 499 journals & proceedings. **Figure 1.** The top 10 journals with the most articles on *artificial intelligence and hotels* Contemporary Hospitality Management, International Journal Of Hospitality Management both have published 19 – 16

Figure 1 shows the top ten journals, which released the greatest quantity of articles on Artificial Intelligence & Hotels.

Among these top ten journals, three journals belong to the Springer, two belong to the Emerald publishing, one belongs to Taylor & Francis publisher, another one belongs to ScienceDirect, one journal belongs to the MDPI (Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute), one belongs to ACM (Association for Computing Machinery), and one belongs to Ceur Workshop Proceedings.

The top most journals are Lecture Notes In Computer Science, including the published lecture notes in bioinformatics and artificial intelligence subseries around 34 papers, International Journal Of papers each respectively. And another top journals are Journal Of Hospitality Marketing And Management and Lecture Notes on Systems and Networks which published 15 -14 paper each, belongs to Taylor & Francis and Springer publishers respectively.

3.2 Year wise publication of papers

The number of papers published between 1984 and 2025 (March) is displayed in Figure 2.

It is evident that over time, there has been an increase in study on hotels and artificial intelligence.

Between 2000 and 2018, there were incredibly few papers published. The number of papers then increased dramatically from 2019 to 2025, going from 40 to 185. Furthermore, the previous five years

have seen the greatest number of publications published. This demonstrates unequivocally how researchers' interest in

this topic has increased significantly in recent years.

Figure 2. Number of papers that have been released over time

3.3 Most Cited Papers.

The most referenced article totaling 605 is “Effect of Covid-19 on Hotel Marketing and Management: A Perspective Article” (Jiang & Wen, 2020). This paper outlines a research agenda from three perspectives: robots and artificial intelligence (AI), cleanliness and hygiene, and health and medical care. First, given the COVID-19 pandemic, various forms of AI (mechanical, thinking, and emotion) may lead to new lines of inquiry at the nexus of hotel management and health emergencies.

The second most cited paper by (Lu et al., 2019) has 556 citations having title “Developing and Validating a service robot integration willingness scale”. In order to identify the critical factors defining customers' long-term willingness to include artificial intelligence and service robots into

routine service transactions, this study aims to develop and test a multi-dimensional Service Robot Integration Willingness (SRIW) Scale. Furthermore, the third-highest cited article by

(Li et al., 2019) “Hotel employee's artificial intelligence and robotics awareness and its impact on turnover intention: The moderating roles of perceived organizational support and competitive psychological climate” has 457 citations This study found that employee turnover intentions are highly impacted by AI and robotics awareness. It also found that the link is moderated by perceived organizational support and competitive psychological climate.

The fourth most cited paper having a total citations of 453, "From high-touch to high-tech: Covid-19 drives robotics adoption" (Zeng et al., 2020). According to this study, the use of robotics and AI in travel and tourism is expected to continue after the COVID-19 pandemic because of the potential for creating robotic applications that improve visitor experiences, safeguarding natural and cultural resources, involving citizens in decisions about tourism

development, and creating new "high-touch" job opportunities for those in the travel, tourism, and hospitality industries.

The fifth and sixth most cited papers by (Kim et al., 2021) and (Akoglu et al., 2021) having citations 383 and 321 respectively. These tests demonstrated a preference for hotels with robot staff rather than those with human staff, and evidence of how perceived threat influences consumers' decisions under extreme emergencies and also to detect fraud in online reviews of the hotels.

Table I lists the top ten most cited papers, with an emphasis on SCOPUS material

Note: *T.C. stands for Scopus total citations

#	Author Names	Paper Title	Year	T.C.*
1	Jiang Y.; Wen J.	Effects of COVID-19 on hotel marketing and management: A Perspective article	2020	605
2	Lu L.; Cai R.; Gursoy D.	Developing and validating a service robot integration willingness scale	2019	556
3	Li J.J.; Bonn M.A.; Ye B.H.	Hotel employee's artificial intelligence and robotics awareness and its impact on turnover intention: The moderating roles of perceived organizational support and competitive psychological climate	2019	457
4	Zeng Z.; Chen P.-J.; Lew A.A.	From high-touch to high-tech: COVID-19 drives robotics adoption	2020	453
5	Kim S.S.; Kim J.; Badu-Baiden F.; Giroux M.; Choi Y.	Preference for robot service or human service in hotels? Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic	2021	383
6	Akoglu L.; Chandy R.; Faloutsos C.	Opinion fraud detection in online reviews by network effects	2021	321
7	Choi Y.; Choi M.; Oh M.; Kim S.	Service robots in hotels: understanding the service quality perceptions of human-robot interaction	2020	312
8	Lin H.; Chi O.H.; Gursoy D.	Antecedents of customers' acceptance of artificially intelligent robotic device use in hospitality services	2020	228
9	Prentice C.; Nguyen M.	Engaging and retaining customers with AI and employee service	2020	210
10	Belanche D.; Casalo L.V.; Flavián C.; Schepers J.	Robots or frontline employees? Exploring customers' attributions of responsibility and stability after service failure or success	2020	206

The later four papers' citation count ranges from 312 to 206. Out of these, the important studies related to artificial intelligence and hotels have been conducted by (Choi et al., 2020), (Lin et al., 2020), (Prentice &

Nguyen, 2020) and (Belanche et al., 2020) examined the role and importance of AI-based technology is going to incorporate in hotels.

3.4 Most prolific authors

Figure 3: The most productive writers

The most prolific authors are listed in Figure 3. Each of the study's 750 publications is the property of its separate 2175 authors.

A list of the top writers with at least two articles was created after the data was analyzed. Additionally, it was discovered that, with six publications, Prof. Ivanov, Stanislav H., is the most prolific author on Artificial Intelligence & Hotels. At the moment, the author is employed at Varna University of Management in Varna, Bulgaria, as a professor. His area of interest in research is the latest developments in artificial intelligence and generative AI in the travel and hospitality sectors. The author with the second-highest output is Dr. Catherine Prentice with five papers. The writer is a professor at the University of Staffordshire, Stoke-on-Trent, UK. His

studies are mainly focused on smart hotel technologies. Along with him, other two prolific authors who also have five paper publications each are Prof. Dendy Rosman and Prof. Craig Webster from Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta Indonesia, and Ball State University, Muncie, United States respectively.

The remaining other prolific authors also published the four research papers are Gajić, T., Khairy, H.A., Kumar, S., & Law, R.. Gajić, Tamara is associated with the Geographical Institute "Jovan Cvijić" of Serbia's Serbian Academy of Arts and Sciences. Prof. Khairy, Hazem Ahmed is currently associated with Sadat City, Egypt's Faculty of Tourism and Hotels.

Sanjeev Kumar is a professor at Lovely Professional University, Paghwara, India.

Rob Law is a faculty at the University of Macau, Macau.

Two authors having three publications each are Anam Afaq and Billy Xiucheng Bai respectively. Prof. Anam Afaq is associated with the Amity University, Noida. While Prof. Billy Xiucheng Bai is a faculty at the University of Nevada, Las Vegas, United States.

3.5 Most prolific countries and institutions

Every paper in this study was written by a separate author from 82 different nations. The top 10 nations with the greatest amount

of papers on AI and hotels are displayed in Figure 4. The first author's country was recognized as the country of origin for the paper. China tops the list with 139 total papers, followed by India having a total of 115 papers published. USA, UK & Spain are the next top countries with the maximum number of papers. Followed by other countries with paper publications ranging from 30 to 15 are Australia, Malaysia, Italy, Turkey, and South Korea respectively. It is important to note that writers from the top three nations contributed more than half (351 total) of the 750 papers in the survey.

Figure 4. Most prolific countries

With a total of 51 papers, the Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Amity University, Griffith University, Lovely Professional University, and Griffith Business School are the most significant institutions in terms of the number of published papers on artificial intelligence and hotels. The University of Nevada, Las Vegas, School of Hotel and

Tourism Management, Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Sun Yat-Sen University, University of Macau, Carnegie Mellon University, Varna University of Management, and numerous other institutions have then contributed more than five papers, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Most prolific institutions

3.6 Co-authorship network analysis

This study does a co-authorship network analysis using the VOSviewer 1.6.20 software. To produce and visualize bibliometric maps, a program known as VOSviewer is utilized. According to (van Eck et al., 2010), it can be used to generate maps of authors or journals using co-citation data or to generate maps of keywords using co-occurrence data. Visualization of Similarities is what VOS stands for. The software uses the VOS mapping technique to create a map (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). The purpose of the co-authorship network analysis is to identify which authors have

co-authored with the greatest number of other authors in the data set and to show the co-authorship networks among the different authors. The data set for this study included 2175 authors in total. Only authors who have co-authored with at least two additional authors in the data set were chosen by the software to produce a network map. According to this criterion, the software discovered that 1329 writers make up the greatest group of authors who have co-authored.

Figure 6. Map of the co-authorship network of various authors, who researched artificial intelligence and hotels

Source: Figure extracted using VOSviewer
The co-authorship network map produced by the VOSviewer program is displayed in Figure 6. Large and small circles joined by multiple lines make up the figure. Larger circles and labels are given to authors who have co-authored with more other authors.

3.7. InterCountry Co-Authorship Network Analysis

The examination of the inter-country co-authorship network is covered in this section. The purpose of this analysis is to determine which authors from which countries have collaborated with the greatest number of authors from other nations. The

inter-country co-authorship network map is displayed in Figure 7. The data set included information from 95 different countries. Out of these numerous nations, the VOSviewer program discovered that 63 were related to one another in terms of co-authorship, with at least two documents per nation. The authors of China, India, the United States, Spain, Turkey, South Korea, and France have coauthored the most with authors from other nations, according to the results of the inter-country co-authorship network analysis. Figure 7 shows that the circle with the labels "China" and "India" has the most lines related to it. Thicker lines are given to nations that have worked together on more papers.

Figure 7. Map of the international co-authorship networks of writers from different nations who have studied hotels and artificial intelligence

Source: Figure extracted using VOSviewer

3.8 Keywords Co-Occurrences Network Analysis

To determine which terms have been used most frequently in the different publications in this study, a keyword co-occurrence network analysis is carried out. This type of study aids in determining the types of subjects and themes on which the researchers have concentrated the most.

The text-mining routine used by VOSviewer builds a map, where the distance between different terms is interpreted as an indication of the relatedness among the various keywords (Laudano et al., 2018). The stronger the relationship between two or

more terms, the smaller the gap between them looks.

To determine the relatedness of the terms, the co-occurrences in the publications were analyzed (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

Figure 8 displays the network map of keyword co-occurrence. There were a total of 4340 keywords in the data collection. To make a network map, only the 202 terms that occurred more than five times in the data set were selected. The map shows the several keywords that are linked to each other by different lines. The lines indicate how frequently these terms have been used together in the papers in the data collection. Further examination of the network map (Figure 8) using the VOSviewer program revealed that "artificial intelligence," "hotels," "hospitality industry" and almost all other maximum-appearing keywords have synonyms for them.

The keywords that have shown up the most indicate that these topics have been the subject of additional investigation.

Figure 9. Keyword cooccurrences network map, highlighting different keywords that appeared alongside the keyword “artificial intelligence” and “hotels”.

Source: Figure extracted using VOSviewer

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the extensive research conducted on Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the hospitality industry, particularly in hotels, over recent years. Addressing the research questions, it is evident that the *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* and *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, which includes *Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence* and *Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics*, have released the greatest quantity of papers in this domain. These journals belong to Emerald Publishing and Springer Publishing, respectively. Notably, the majority of research has been carried out in the last five years, with 2024 being the most prolific year for publications.

In this field, the most cited paper is “Effect of Covid-19 on hotel marketing and management: A perspective article” (Jiang & Wen, 2020), which has accumulated 605

citations. Among researchers, Prof. Stanislav H. Ivanov is recognized as the most prolific

author. Additionally, China and India emerge as the leading contributors in terms of research output, with their authors frequently collaborating with scholars from other countries. The institutions making the most significant contributions to this research area include The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Amity University, Griffith University, and Lovely Professional University.

According to a keyword co-occurrence network analysis, the terms that appear most frequently in this study are “artificial intelligence,” “hospitality,” “hotels,” “hotel industry,” “machine learning,” and “service robots.”

Despite the comprehensive nature of this bibliometric analysis, certain Limitations need to be recognized. First, the research considers only publications from 1984 to March 2025, suggesting that future research could expand this timeline. Secondly, since the research depends entirely on the SCOPUS database, it excludes research published in non-SCOPUS-indexed journals.

Future studies could incorporate other databases, such as Web of Science (WoS), to offer a more comprehensive holistic perspective. Furthermore, only English-language publications were analyzed, leaving out valuable research available in other languages. Additionally, unpublished works, PhD theses, master's dissertations, and other academic reports were not included in this study, presenting another avenue for future research.

Given these limitations, this study is not exhaustive in capturing all aspects of AI research in the hotel industry. However, it still offers a thorough bibliometric analysis and incorporates significant academic contributions in the field. Ultimately, this research serves as a valuable resource, shedding new light on the intersection of AI and hospitality. It is expected to provide meaningful insights for researchers interested in advancing this field further.

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